

Hybrid rice

Evaluation of hybrid rices for ratooning ability

J. S. Chauhan, S. S. Virmani, R. Aquino, and B. S. Vergara, IRRI

Hybrid rice was developed in China. About 6 million ha of irrigated land are planted to F₁ hybrids that yield 20-30% more than the best semidwarf, nonhybrid varieties. Hybrid rice also should yield well in some rainfed lowland conditions on account of their early seedling and vegetative vigor and strong, deep, root system. A successful ratoon from the hybrid rice crop under rainfed lowland conditions might help compensate for the extra cost of hybrid seed, which is estimated to be three to four times more than that of nonhybrid varieties.

We evaluated 57 rice hybrids and 5 check varieties for ratooning ability at the IRRI farm in the 1983 dry season.

Hybrids and checks were ratooned by cutting the stalks 15 cm above the ground at maturity. Immediately after cutting 40 kg N/ha was topdressed. Ratooning ability was rated 3 weeks later.

Ratooning ability varied widely. IR56 and 14 hybrids performed consistently well in 2 or more replications. Mean regeneration for hybrids varied from 62 to 97% (see table). However, all had 70% or higher regeneration in at least 2 replications. IR56 had 90 to 100% regenerations, except in 1 of 9 plots where it had only 40 to 50%. However, it had only 10-11 tillers/hill and 8-9 panicles/hill. In some hybrids with relatively poor regeneration, missing hills were compensated for by the many tillers and panicles per successful hill. Hybrid ratoons were more vigorous than those of IR56.

Ratoon height Varied from 51 cm to 70 cm. Hybrid IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR36 had the most tillers and panicles/m². Because the experiment ended before maturity, number of tillers and panicles/m² may not truly reflect yield potential.

Hybrids with IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A in their parentage had high regeneration and vigorous ratoons. Because the parents of

Plant characters of rice hybrids screened for ratooning ability. IRRI, 1983 dry season (av of 3 replications).

Hybrid, variety	Regeneration (%)	Plant ht (cm)	Total tillers (no./m ²)	Tillers (no./hill)	Total panicles (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./hill)	Viral disease rating
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR56 ^a	70	65	279	11	189	8	1
IR10154-23-3-3A/IR15795-232-3-3-2 ^b	69	51	323	13	149	6	1
IR56 (check)	81	62	284	10	179	6	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR36 ^a	97	65	515	15	423	12	1
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR48 ^c	81	60	389	14	145	6	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR19661-364-1-2-3 ^b	68	61	329	14	171	8	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR19735-5-2-3-2-1 ^a	93	64	485	15	420	13	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR19729-67-3	83	68	301	10	246	8	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR13146-45-2-3 ^d	62	58	325	15	401 ^d	18	0
IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR10781-143-2-3 ^e	68	—	346	15	—	—	0
IR19799-17-3-1-1A/IR13420-6-3-3-1	83	55	349	12	231	8	0
IR19799-17-3-1-1A/IR2797-125-3-2-2	81	70	353	12	274	10	1
IR56 (check)	93	60	348	11	294	9	0
MR365A/IR19661-364-1-2-3 ^a	68	69	327	14	218	9	0
MR365A/IR19661-131-1-2 ^b	64	67	337	15	213	10	0
MR365A/IR48	80	65	378	14	307	9	1
IR56 (check)	93	56	348	11	307	9	0

^a In one replication, plants were mostly vegetative, flowering started. ^b In more than one replication, plants were mostly vegetative, flowering started. ^c Based on two replications; in third replication, plants were in Vegetative phase. ^d Based on one replication; in two other replications, flowering did not occur. ^e Vegetative plants only in all three replications.

the hybrids were not evaluated, it is difficult to predict the bases of good ratooning ability. Whether this parent line has dominant genes for ratooning ability or whether ratooning resulted from heterosis needs further investigation. In one of the crosses (IR19657-34-2-2-3-3A/IR36), however, good ratooning ability seems to be due to dominant gene(s) in the parent line because IR36 showed consistently poor ratooning.

Different responses of some hybrids and IR56 in different replications suggested that besides genetic factors, cultural management factors may influence ratooning ability. F₂ populations of the hybrids and their parents should be evaluated for ratooning in subsequent studies. □

New maintainers and restorers for Chinese cytoplasmic-genetic male-sterile lines

M. A. Hassan and E. A. Siddiq, Genetics Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, India

We sought to identify new maintainers and restorers for the Chinese male-sterile lines: Zhen Shan 97A, Er-Jiu- Nan 1A, and V20A.

Bhavani, BPI 76-1/CO 42, Basmati mutant, and Pusa 169-33-1-1 are good maintainers. CRM 13-32-1 11 and ADT33 are partial maintainers which have not been reported until now (Table 1). We also identified three new restorers: IR30, Pusa 150-21-1-1, and Pusa 167- 120-3-2 (Table 2). Although they are good